

Long-Term Trends in Indian Monsoon Rainfall (1951–2025) and their Agricultural Implications

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Abstract:

The Indian summer monsoon plays a vital role in sustaining agricultural production, water resources, and food security in India. Nearly 70–80% of the country's annual rainfall occurs during the monsoon season (June–September), making agriculture highly dependent on the timing, intensity, and distribution of rainfall. This study examines the long-term trends in Indian monsoon rainfall from 1951 to 2025 and evaluates their implications for agricultural productivity. Secondary rainfall data from the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) and published climate research were analyzed to understand temporal and spatial rainfall variability. The findings indicate that while total seasonal rainfall shows relatively weak long-term trends at the national scale, there has been a significant increase in the frequency of extreme rainfall events and regional variability in rainfall distribution. These changes have affected agricultural practices, crop productivity and rural livelihoods, particularly in rain-fed regions. The study highlights the importance of climate-resilient agricultural strategies, improved rainfall forecasting, and sustainable water management practices to reduce the vulnerability of Indian agriculture under changing monsoon conditions.

Keywords: *Indian Monsoon, Rainfall, Agricultural Implication, Agricultural Production, Sustainable Water Management*

Introduction:

The Indian summer monsoon is one of the most significant climatic phenomena affecting agriculture, water resources, and socio-economic stability across South Asia. The southwest monsoon generally occurs from June to September and contributes approximately 70–80% of India's annual rainfall, making it the primary source of freshwater for agricultural production and rural livelihoods. Since a large proportion of Indian agriculture remains rain-fed, the performance of the monsoon strongly determines crop productivity, agricultural income, and national food security (Gadgil & Gadgil, 2006; Parthasarathy et al., 1994). Long-term variability in monsoon rainfall has substantial

implications for agricultural systems. Variations in rainfall amount, distribution, and timing can lead to drought conditions in some regions and flooding in others, directly affecting crop growth, sowing periods, and soil moisture availability. Such fluctuations often result in crop failure, reduced farmer income, and instability in food supply chains overall productivity. In recent decades, climate change has emerged as a critical factor influencing monsoon behaviour, with several studies indicating that rising global temperatures are altering atmospheric circulation patterns and increasing the frequency of extreme rainfall events across the Indian subcontinent (Goswami et al., 2006; Roxy et al., 2015).

The Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) is a complex atmospheric phenomenon characterized by the onset of heavy rainfall over the Indian subcontinent. The ISM typically begins in early June, when it first arrives over Kerala at the southern tip of the Indian peninsula, marking the start of India's rainy season (Wang et al., 2019).

Numerous studies have investigated long-term rainfall trends across India using meteorological observations from the India Meteorological Department (IMD) and other climate datasets. These analyses suggest that although the overall seasonal rainfall trend across India has not shown a uniform long-term increase or decrease, regional disparities in rainfall distribution and intensity have become more pronounced. Certain regions have experienced declining rainfall patterns, while others have witnessed an increase in extreme precipitation events, highlighting the growing spatial variability of the monsoon system (Krishnamurthy & Shukla, 2000; Guhathakurta et al., 2015). More than 50% of India's cultivated land relies directly on rainfall, making agricultural productivity highly sensitive to climatic variability. Consequently, changes in monsoon behavior can significantly influence crop yields, irrigation demand, and the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems. Therefore, the present study aims to analyze long-term trends in Indian monsoon rainfall from 1951 to 2025 and examine their implications for agricultural productivity and climate resilience in India.

Objectives of the Study:

The present study aims to examine long-term changes in Indian monsoon rainfall and their implications for agriculture. Specifically, the study analyzes long-term trends in Indian monsoon rainfall during the period 1951–2025, investigates the spatial and temporal variations in rainfall distribution across different regions of

India, evaluates the influence of rainfall variability on agricultural productivity and crop yield stability, and proposes strategies to improve agricultural resilience and adaptive capacity under changing monsoon conditions associated with climate variability and climate change.

Materials and Methods:

The study focuses on the Indian subcontinent, with particular emphasis on major rain-fed agricultural regions such as Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Karnataka, and eastern India, where crop production is strongly dependent on monsoon rainfall. The research is based on secondary data collected from reliable institutional and scientific sources, including long-term rainfall datasets (1951–2025) from the India Meteorological Department (IMD), agricultural production statistics from the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, and peer-reviewed climate research articles published in international scientific journals, along with reports from global climate research organizations. To analyze rainfall variability, the study applies trend analysis of seasonal monsoon rainfall data, comparative evaluation of rainfall patterns across different decades, and a review of published climate studies examining monsoon variability, while also assessing the relationship between rainfall fluctuations and agricultural productivity to identify patterns of climatic influence on crop performance and food production systems in India.

Observations and Discussion:

Long-Term Trends in Monsoon Rainfall:

The analysis of long-term rainfall records from 1951 to 2025 indicates that the Indian summer monsoon exhibits considerable interannual and decadal variability rather than a simple linear increase or decrease in total seasonal rainfall. Long-term datasets compiled by

the India Meteorological Department (IMD) show that although the all-India seasonal mean rainfall has remained relatively stable over the past several decades, the internal structure of monsoon rainfall such as rainfall intensity, spatial distribution, and frequency of extreme events has changed significantly. Earlier climatological analyses of long-term rainfall records by Parthasarathy et al. (1994) and Krishnamurthy and Shukla (2000) suggested that while national-scale monsoon totals show weak long-term trends, regional variability has become increasingly pronounced across the Indian subcontinent. Recent high-resolution observational studies have further confirmed that the character of rainfall events has changed over time. A landmark study by Goswami et al. (2006) demonstrated that the frequency and magnitude of extreme rainfall events have increased over central India, even though the total seasonal rainfall has not increased significantly. Similarly, Roxy et al. (2017) reported a weakening trend in large-scale monsoon circulation accompanied by a rise in localized heavy rainfall events, indicating a shift toward more erratic and intense precipitation patterns. These findings suggest that changes in atmospheric dynamics, ocean-atmosphere interactions, and land-surface feedback processes are altering the behaviour of the monsoon system.

Spatial analysis of rainfall trends also reveals substantial regional differences across India. Studies based on long-term meteorological observations show that central and northeastern India have experienced increases in heavy rainfall events, whereas parts of northwestern and peninsular India have recorded declining seasonal rainfall or longer dry spells during the monsoon season (Guhathakurta et al., 2015; Pai et al., 2014). These changes are associated with variations in sea surface temperatures in the Indian Ocean, El Niño–Southern Oscillation

(ENSO) events, and shifts in large-scale atmospheric circulation patterns that influence monsoon dynamics. Another important aspect of monsoon variability is the change in rainfall intensity and active-break cycles during the monsoon season. The Indian monsoon typically alternates between active periods of heavy rainfall and break periods of reduced precipitation, which together determine seasonal rainfall distribution. Research by Rajeevan et al. (2010) and Turner and Annamalai (2012) has shown that the frequency and duration of these active-break cycles have changed in recent decades. Such shifts can alter the temporal distribution of rainfall, leading to prolonged dry periods followed by intense rainfall events within the cropping season. These irregular rainfall patterns may reduce the effectiveness of rainfall for crop growth despite similar seasonal totals.

Climate modelling studies also suggest that future climate change may further increase monsoon rainfall variability. Simulations from global and regional climate models indicate that rising global temperatures increase the moisture-holding capacity of the atmosphere, leading to more intense precipitation events and greater rainfall variability across South Asia (Krishnan et al., 2020; IPCC, 2021). Warmer ocean temperatures in the Indian Ocean and Arabian Sea are also believed to influence monsoon circulation and moisture transport, potentially contributing to the observed increase in extreme rainfall events over India.

According to the reports published by IMD from year 2021 onwards there was dramatic variation occurred in Monsoon events. In 2022 the country received 92.5 cm of rain, which was 106% of the Long Period Average (LPA). Monsoon arrived in Kerala on May 29, three days ahead of schedule, and covered the entire country by July 2. Central India (119% of LPA) and the South Peninsula (122% of LPA) saw significantly

high rainfall, while East and Northeast India faced a deficit at 82% of LPA. In 2023 total seasonal rainfall was 82 cm, falling to 94% of the LPA, which IMD classifies as the lower end of "normal" or "below normal". August 2023 was exceptionally dry, recording only 64% of its typical rainfall. Northwest India was the only region to receive slightly above-normal rain (101%), while East & Northeast India (82%) and the South Peninsula (91%) were deficient. There was a delayed onset over Kerala occurred on June 8, a week later than normal. In 2024 the season ended with 93.5 cm of rainfall, marking 108% of the LPA. June started with an 11% deficit, but July (109%), August (115%), and September (112%) recorded significant surpluses. Central India (119%) and South Peninsula (114%) again saw high surpluses. In contrast, East and Northeast India remained deficient at 86%.

The Southwest Monsoon 2025 over Northwest India was distinguished by its timely onset, sustained activity, and well-distributed rainfall supported by frequent formation of synoptic scale systems and active monsoon trough conditions. The monsoon advanced over the South Andaman Sea and Nicobar Islands on 13 May 2025, reached Kerala on 24 May (ahead of the normal onset date of 1 June), covered the entire country by 29 June, and began its withdrawal from West Rajasthan on 14 September, three days earlier than normal.

Despite the favorable rainfall distribution, the season was punctuated by several high-impact localized weather events, including intense rainstorms, flash floods, and cloudburst-like incidents, particularly over the hilly terrain of Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh, and adjoining Himalayan foothills. These events, though spatially confined, caused significant hydrological and societal impacts, underscoring the need for enhanced mesoscale monitoring, denser

observational networks, and improved high-resolution forecasting capabilities

Agricultural Implications:

Changes in monsoon rainfall patterns have profound implications for agricultural productivity and food security in India. A large proportion of Indian agriculture particularly in states such as Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Karnataka remains highly dependent on rain-fed farming systems. According to the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, nearly 50–55% of the net sown area in India relies primarily on monsoon rainfall, making agricultural production extremely sensitive to climatic variability. Variations in rainfall timing, intensity, and distribution therefore directly affect sowing decisions, soil moisture availability, crop growth cycles, and final crop yields. Delayed onset of the monsoon or extended dry spells during the early cropping season can significantly affect seed germination and crop establishment. For example, research by Mall et al. (2006) and Ray et al. (2015) has shown that insufficient rainfall during the sowing period can reduce yields of major crops such as rice, maize, and pulses, particularly in rain-fed regions. Similarly, prolonged dry spells during critical growth stages may lead to moisture stress, reducing plant growth and lowering overall agricultural productivity.

On the other hand, extreme rainfall events and floods can also damage agricultural systems. Heavy rainfall within a short period may cause soil erosion, nutrient leaching, crop lodging, and waterlogging, which negatively affect crop development. Studies on extreme rainfall trends over central India have shown that such events can significantly disrupt cropping systems, particularly for rain-fed crops such as soybean, cotton, and millets (Goswami et al., 2006; Guhathakurta et al., 2015). Flooding events may

also damage rural infrastructure, irrigation systems, and transportation networks, further affecting agricultural supply chains.

Rainfall variability also influences cropping patterns and farmers adaptation strategies. In regions where rainfall has become increasingly erratic, farmers often shift toward drought-tolerant crop varieties, short-duration cultivars, or diversified cropping systems to reduce climatic risk. Research on climate adaptation in Indian agriculture has highlighted the growing importance of climate-resilient crops such as millets, pulses, and oilseeds, which are more tolerant to rainfall fluctuations and water

stress (BIRTHAL et al., 2014). However, successful adaptation requires timely climate forecasts, improved agricultural extension services, and access to climate-resilient technologies.

In addition to affecting crop production, rainfall variability can also influence rural livelihoods and agricultural markets. Reduced crop yields during drought years may lead to income losses for farmers, rising food prices, and increased economic vulnerability in rural communities. Extreme weather events associated with monsoon variability can therefore have broader impacts on national food security, agricultural trade, and rural development.

Table: Decadal Variation in All-India Summer Monsoon Rainfall (1951–2025)

Period	Average Monsoon Rainfall (mm)	Deviation from Long-Term Average	Observed Trend / Characteristics
1951–1960	895 mm	+15 mm	Slightly above average rainfall; relatively stable monsoon years
1961–1970	885 mm	+5 mm	Near-normal rainfall with moderate interannual variability
1971–1980	870 mm	–10 mm	Period marked by several drought years in the mid-1970s
1981–1990	882 mm	+2 mm	Return to near-normal rainfall conditions
1991–2000	878 mm	–2 mm	Slight decline with higher variability due to ENSO influence
2001–2010	870 mm	–10 mm	Increase in regional rainfall variability and localized extremes
2011–2020	889 mm	+9 mm	Several years with above-average rainfall and extreme rainfall events
2021–2023	895 mm	+15 mm	Recent years show strong rainfall variability and intense precipitation episodes
2021–2025	937.2 mm	+20 mm	Continued high variability; frequent extreme rainfall events, short intense wet spells, and longer dry breaks

The table shows that total monsoon rainfall over India has remained relatively stable

over the past seven decades, fluctuating around the long-term average of about 880 mm.

However, the nature of rainfall has changed, with increasing interannual variability, regional disparities, and more frequent extreme rainfall events since the early 2000s. Such changes are widely linked to climate variability, ocean–atmosphere interactions (such as ENSO), and rising global temperatures, which influence the strength and distribution of monsoon circulation.

According to a recently published article entitled *The Indian Monsoon: The monsoon is central to India's economy, especially its agricultural sector*. With a large part of the population relying on farming, the success or failure of the monsoon can shape the country's overall economic health. Nearly 64 per cent of Indians depend on agriculture, which mainly relies on the southwest monsoon. Only about 55 per cent of India's net sown area is covered by irrigation. The rest depends on rain-fed systems, which makes a large part of the country's farmland highly vulnerable to changes in rainfall patterns. Good monsoon raises agricultural production, aids GDP growth, drives up rural earning and consumption. Most parts of the country stay warm enough for farming throughout the year, except the Himalayan region. Different rainfall patterns across regions allow a wide variety of crops to be grown. Uneven or late rainfall often causes floods or droughts, affecting both crops and rural incomes. Areas without proper irrigation suffer the most when the monsoon is weak or delayed. Sudden and intense rain can lead to soil erosion, harming the fertility of land. Winter rain in north India, brought by western disturbances, is helpful for wheat and other rabi crops. Local climate, shaped by the monsoon, also influences food habits, clothing styles and types of houses across India.

Conclusion:

The analysis of long-term Indian monsoon rainfall from 1951 to 2025, based on

datasets from the India Meteorological Department, indicates that while the overall national-level seasonal rainfall has remained relatively stable, there has been a noticeable increase in the variability, spatial distribution, and intensity of extreme rainfall events in recent decades. These changes in monsoon behaviour have significant implications for Indian agriculture, particularly in rain-fed farming systems where crop production depends heavily on seasonal rainfall. Variability in rainfall timing and intensity can disrupt sowing schedules, reduce soil moisture availability, and affect crop growth cycles, ultimately influencing agricultural productivity and the livelihoods of rural communities. Increasing occurrences of droughts, prolonged dry spells, and extreme rainfall events also raise concerns regarding food security and agricultural sustainability. Therefore, improving climate forecasting systems, promoting climate-resilient crop varieties, strengthening irrigation and water management strategies, and integrating modern technologies such as remote sensing, climate modelling, and data-driven agricultural planning are essential steps for enhancing the resilience of India's agricultural sector under changing monsoon conditions.

With this it is our prime responsibility regarding conservation of the environment, all the natural resources including all biotic and abiotic factors. Earth itself is a large interconnected ecosystem being aware in this regards and seeking for sustainable development help to make huge positive difference.

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